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Drug Abuse and Resistance to Peer Influence as Predictors of Criminal Behaviour Among Youths in Aguata LGA of Anambra State in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study examined drug abuse and resistance to peer influence as predictors of criminal behaviour among youths in Aguata Local Government Area of Anambra State Nigeria. Specifically, the study aimed to find out the extent to which drug abuse and resistance to peer influence will significantly predict criminal behaviour among youths in Aguata Local Government Area of Anambra State. The study also determine the extent to which drug abuse and resistance to peer influence will jointly predict criminal behaviour among youths in Aguata Local Government Area of Anambra State. The participants that were used for this study are youths in Aguata local government area in Anambra state. Two-hundred (200) youths were selected through purposive sampling method. Three instruments were utilized in this study, the instruments are; Crime Behaviour Rating Scale (CBRS) by Animasahun (2011), Drug Abuse Screening Test by Skinner (1982) and Resistance to Peer Influence Scale (RPI; Steinberg & Monahan, 2007). A predictive design was adopted for this study. Three hypotheses were tested using multiple regression and the findings showed that; drug abuse positively and significantly predicted criminal behaviour. Also, resistance to peer influence negatively and significantly predicted criminal behaviour. Finally, drug abuse and resistance to peer influence jointly predicted criminal behaviour in among youths in Aguata Local Government of Anambra State. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that there is crucial need to address drug related problems among youths.

Keywords: Crime, Criminal Behaviour, Drug Abuse, Peer Influence, Youth

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Our society today is bedeviled with high rate of criminal behaviour and all manner of criminality. Thus any right thinking individual should feel concerned because of their adverse effects. There is a growing perception about the prevalence of criminal behaviour and criminality among the youths. Youths' involvement in violence and criminality seems to be on the increase, especially in high-profile crimes like kidnapping, armed robbery, ritual killings, murder, advance fee fraud (popularly known as 419), and drug trafficking (Ajaegbu, 2012, Animasahun, 2011, & Aremu, 2011). Many youths are expected to be within the university system, where they are supposed to develop skills required for both career and psycho-social development (Fredricks, Blumenfeld & Paris, 2004, Larson, 2000; Tsang, Law & Hui, 2012). Unfortunately, evidence from Nigeria Prison Services indicated that about 70% of the inmates (both awaiting trial and convicted) are within the age range (18-30 years) that could be described as youths (Nigerian Prison, 2017). Globally, Nigerian youths within these ages who are incarcerated overseas from 2020 till date are even higher (David, 2020; Okakwu, 2021; Nwafor, 2022,). Furthermore, there are a

good percentage of individuals within this age range who may not have been arrested or convicted but might have been involved in one way or the other in various forms of criminal behaviour including rape, cultism, armed robbery, internet scam, drug trafficking, kidnapping, murder, burglary, terrorism, bribery and corruption, money laundering and others (Ojo, Ajasa, Oladipupo & Aderinto, 2021; Okafor, et al, 2020); National Daily Newspaper, 2017). Evidence from research showed that there is an increase in crime in Nigeria (Achuba, Ighomereho & Akpor-Robaro, 2013; Adegoke, 2014; Ajaegbu, 2012; National Bureau of Statistics, 2017; Nigerian Communication Commission, 2020). Internationally, Nigeria is ranked 16th in the world index of insecurity and crime (Global Peace Index, 2020; Nigerian Communication Commission, 2019). The implication of these high incidences of criminal behaviour includes the fact that fewer investors may be willing to invest in Nigeria, life and properties are not secured, more offenders may be incarcerated, making the prisons to be stressed and overcrowded, and victims will suffer more trauma and psychological symptoms.

Generally, crime is defined from a legal perspective as acts or omissions, use of force, fraud, or stealth to obtain material or symbolic resources; that can be punished by imprisonment or fine (Maloma, 2017; Hansen et al, 2021; Onyeaka et al, 2020). In other words, criminal behaviour is an illegal act for which someone can be punished by a constituted authority especially a gross violation of law; a grave offence against humanity. Examples of criminal behaviour are kidnapping, murder, burglary, fraud, rape, terrorism, armed robbery, cyber-crimes, bribery and corruption, money laundry, and so on. Criminal behaviour oftentimes represents a collective response that is directed by subcultural values and norms of distinct collectivities such as peer groups within the larger group. Individuals in society will usually make friends or have their closest associates from among their peer groups. Therefore, peer associates and drug abuse have a great influence on the lifestyle of their members. Drug abuse is a maladaptive use of a drug, resulting in impairment of functioning or distress, as manifested by a failure to perform adequately at home, school, or work (Akenzua, 2021). Drug abuse has to do with an individual who is using a drug when there is no legitimate medical need to do so or who is drinking more than accepted social standards and is said to be abusing that chemical (Ozah, 2021). Drug abuse is a harmful pattern of use of any substance for mood-altering purposes which leads to frequent and serious problems. These problems can affect performance at school, work, or home. Many times, relationships (such as with friends and parents) begin to suffer due to substance abuse. Individuals that engaged in abusing substances often have trouble with the law.

The main purpose of this study is to find out if drug abuse and resistance to peer influence will predict criminal behaviour among youths in Aguata Local Government Area of Anambra State. Specifically, this study seeks to: determine the extent to which drug abuse and resistance to peer influence will significantly predict criminal behaviour among youths in Aguata Local Government Area of Anambra State. To determine the extent to which drug abuse and resistance to peer influence will jointly predict criminal behaviour among youths in Aguata Local Government Area of Anambra State. In line with the above main purpose and specific purpose, this study is guided by the following research question: To what extent will drug abuse and resistance to peer influence predict criminal behaviour among youths in Aguata local Government Area of Anambra State? In what ways will drug abuse and resistance to peer influence predict criminal behaviour among youths in Aguata Local Government Area of Anambra State?

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Review

Crime and Criminal Behaviour

Crime is an action or omission that violates a law, constitutes an offence, or an illegal act that results in punishments that can range from the payment of fines to incarceration in jail which constitutes an offence and is punishable by law (Criminal-law free advice, 2016). Robertson (1990) defined crime in ordinary language as regulations that are created and enforced through social or organizational institutions to control human behaviour. In other words, crime in legal terms can be seen as acts or omissions forbidden by law that can be punished by imprisonment and/ or fine. Examples of crimes are murder, armed

robbery, burglary, rape, drunken driving, child neglect, and failure to pay taxes when due. It is something reprehensible, foolish, or disgraceful e.g.; it is a crime to steal. So, whether a given act or omission constitutes a crime does not depend on the nature of that act or omission. It depends on the nature of the legal consequences that may follow it. So, an act or omission is a crime if it is capable of being followed by what is called criminal proceedings.

Drug Abuse

A drug is a substance used for medical purposes that change the function of the body. Chukwuleta (2021), perceived a drug as any substance which upon entering the body changes the body's function and structure. Drug abuse is substance abuse or disorder that is characterized by a destructive pattern of using a substance that leads to significant problems or distress (Njoku 2021). Chukwuleta (2021) sees drug abuse as the scenario when the drug is taken more than it is prescribed. It could also be seen as the use of illicit drugs, or the abuse of prescription or over-the-counter drugs. He further noted that drug abuse is the deliberate use of chemical substances for reasons other than intended medical purposes and which occasioned physical, mental, emotional, or social impairment to the users. Drug addiction also called substance dependent or chemical dependency is a disease that is characterized by a destructive pattern of drug abuse that leads to significant problems involving tolerance, to or withdrawal from the substance, as well as other problems that use of the substance can cause to sufferer, either socially or in terms of their work or school performance (Akpabio, 2019).

A drug addict is said to be someone whose life has become dependent on drugs, hence drug abuse (Okoli et al, 2021). Drug addiction is dependence on a legal or illegal drug or medication, drug addiction can cause serious, long-term consequences, including problems with physical and mental health, relationship, and the law (Maloma, 2017). Drug use and substance abuse is a form of deviant behavior or a manifestation of juvenile delinquency. Deviant behavior is that which a considerable number of people in society regard as reprehensive and beyond the limits of tolerance (Ugwu, 2021, Maloma, 2017). For society to continue, social order has to be maintained, social order makes human interaction possible and has certain expectations in the society, this is achieved through social controls. Inadequate social controls lead to chaos that would result and will be manifested in massive institutional breakdown and malfunctioning (Nelson, 2021).

Through the socialization process, members of a society are trained to fit into society by acquiring ways of thinking, feeling, and acting characterized by their society's culture. By internalizing the society's way of thinking, feeling, and acting the individual can translate social control into self-control. Thus, the way members of a society are socialized to a greater extent determines their behavior, consequently inadequate or poor socialization of youth results in deviant behavior like drug use among secondary school students. This problem could also be an indicator that many youths are inadequately socialized. This situation may point to the fact that the institutions for socializing youths into responsible adults for instance the family are failing and that the moral structures of society require re-examination (Nelson, 2021). The various abused drugs and substances used by the students can be classified into the following categories: i.) Stimulants: e.g. cocaine, nicotine, and amphetamines. ii.) Hallucinogens: e.g. Lysergic Diethyl Amide (LSD). iii.) Narcotics: e.g. Cigarettes. iv.) Tobacco. v.) Psychotropic: e.g. Anti-depressants, Antipsychotic.

History of Substance Use and Abuse

As previously mentioned, substance use is strongly ingrained in our history, with the earliest reported use of opium being by the Sumerians in 5000 B.C. (Schaffer Library, n.d.). This long-running history of substance use and abuse has always created challenges for our society, with substances being a vital part of our economy, being used to increase agricultural production, to creating financial strains on our medical system through prevention, treatment, and incarceration programs (Schaffer Library, n.d.). However, some substances were widely accepted for everyday use when they were first discovered, such as cocaine used by psychologists, LSD given to soldiers by governments, and opium for medicinal purposes (Schaffer Library, n.d.). In addition, in many societies, caffeine, nicotine, and alcohol (which are

extremely addictive) are utilized by most individuals in their daily lives, despite the harmful effects they can have on the body.

The Global Situation on Drug Abuse

Drug abuse has become a global problem, (world Drug Report 2000,) there is hardly any country that has not been affected by this problem. At least 134 countries and territories were faced with a drug abuse problem in the 1990s. Its estimated 1 billion men and 250 million women smoke bhang with the vast majority living in low-income and middle-income countries (World Bank 2000). It kills an estimated 4 million by the end of 2000 and is projected to kill 8.4million people by 2020 (WHO 2000), while some 1.1billion people globally smoke cigarettes, an estimated 2billion people worldwide consume alcoholic beverages of whom 763million have diagnosable alcohol consumption serious health and social consequences mainly through intoxication, alcohol dependence and other biomedical effects on the substance.

Studies by the United Nations Drugs Control Programme (UNDCP) provide insight into the global spread of drug abuse. "Global Illicit Drug Trends" was compiled from questionnaires sent to national governments requesting information on drug seizures by police and customs officials. "The Drug Nexus in Africa" was drawn from information forwarded by drug control agencies in 10 African states. In the language of statistics, they provide an overview of the scale and depth of drug use internationally. The African report in particular sheds some light on the social, economic, and political origins of drug taking. "Global Illicit Drug Trends" points out that the illicit drug trade is a complex and massive global industry, with markets in every country of the world. The growth in world commerce and the explosion in global finance markets have made it much easier for drug cartels to move their money around and obscure the source of the immense profits being made by the criminal syndicates controlling the trade.

Peer Influence

Peer influence as people grow older, they are faced with some challenging decisions (Steinberg & Monahan, 2017). Some don't have a clear right or wrong answer. Other decisions involve serious moral questions. Making decisions is hard enough, and can be even harder when pressured by other people. People of the same age group, like classmates, or workmates are called peers. Your peers are the people with whom you identify and spend time with. In adults, peers may be determined less by age and more by shared interests or professions.

They heavily influence one's behavior, and get one into doing something. Peer influence occurs when an individual experiences implied or expressed persuasion to adopt similar values, beliefs, and goals, or to participate in the same activities as those in the peer group. It's something everyone has to deal with, even adults (News Agency of Nigeria, 2021). Paying attention to own feelings and beliefs about what is right and wrong can help in knowing the right thing to do. Inner strength and self-confidence can help one to stand firm, walk away, and resist doing something when they know better. Therefore, peer influence exists for all ages and no one is immune to peer influence.

Peer influence can be either expressed or implied. In expressed peer pressure, an individual is challenged directly to comply with existing norms. Studies show that both peers are inclined to take risks they do not want to take because they believe the risky behavior will increase their standing in the eyes of their peers and assure their acceptance in the group (Chikezie et al, 2021).

Implied peer influence is more subtle and can be harder to combat. For example, a group of peers may make fun of the way another peer is dressed up, pressuring members of their group to dress only in one acceptable style. Often young people who look, dress, or act differently, or who have significant interests that differ from those of their age group become outcasts because of the influence groups place on their members not to associate with anyone unlike themselves (Plüddemann et al, 2010). This can lead the rejected person to feel desperate and depressed. Adult peer influence can be challenging when an individual is trying to fit in a certain group given the fact that resources are a key factor here. It is all about the social class of an individual in the society which is a result of the socialization process that one was exposed to. Having good company is everyone's wish but that may not be the case once there is low self-esteem. To curb the challenge, adults begin to work on areas that will help them fit in a given peer

group (Famuyiwa, 2011). By the time a person reaches the age of forty in a professional or managerial career, it is clear whether he or she will make it to the top of the field. If individuals have not reached their goals by this time, most adjust their level of aspirations and in some cases start over in a new career. Many however are unable to recognize that they have unrealistic aspirations and thus suffer from considerable stress.

Erikson (1974) stated that the primary psychosocial task of middle adulthood-ages 45-65 years is to develop generatively or the desire to expand one's influence and commitment to family, society, and future generations (Chukwuka, 2015). In other words, middle adulthood is concerned with forming and guiding the next generation. The middle adult who fails to develop generatively, experiences stagnation, and self-absorption with its associated self-indulgence and invalidism. Studies show that most adult peer influence is about not taking action because, as one gets older, they fear change. Not only do they fear change for themselves, but also for their friends because if they change, we might have to change too (Bibb & Darley, 2018).

Theoretical Review

This study is anchored on differential association theory by Edwin Sutherland (1883-1950) and social exchange theory (George Homans, 1958).

Differential Association Theory

This theory was developed by Edwin Sutherland (1883-1950) proposing that through interaction with others, individuals learn the values, attitudes, techniques, and motives for behaviour. Individuals learn how to commit criminal acts; drives, and rationalizations. Their inspiration is the processes of cultural transmission and construction. Sutherland had developed the idea of the "self" as a social construct, as when a person's self-image is continuously being reconstructed especially when interacting with other people. The theory predicts that an individual will choose the criminal path when the balance of definitions for law-breaking exceeds those for law-abiding. This tendency will be reinforced if social association provides active people in the person's life. Earlier in life the individual comes under the influence of those of high status within that group, the more likely the individual to follow in their footsteps. There is no natural, innate manner in which people interact with one another rather; humans learn how to behave in social situations whether properly or improperly. These simple ideas are not disputed today, but this was not the case when sociologist Edwin Sutherland advanced the argument that an individual undergoes the same basic socialization process whether learning conformity or deviant acts. The theory is outlined in nine propositions.

The first proposition posits that criminal behaviour is learned. (Sutherland and Cressey, 1978), just as one learns to tie his or her shoelaces or to prepare a meal, so too does one learn to pick a lock or copy a credit card. The skills and techniques required for criminal activity are not innovations, and they are not automatically obtained from birth, or through associations with criminals; rather, they are acquired through a process of learning. In the second proposition, Sutherland refutes the possibility that criminals and drug abusers must witness criminal behavior to learn it. Rather, he states that one learns criminal behaviour through social interaction and communication (Sutherland & Cressey, 1978). Sutherland's third proposition begins to explain the observations of Shaw and McKay (1979), who observed consistently high rates of learning among members of similar social conditions. He argues that most learning of crime and drug abuse takes place in interaction with members of intimate, personal groups and that methods of impersonal communication such as television, films, or newspaper are less influential this effective in learning (Sutherland & Cressey, 1978:123). The fourth proposition expands Sutherland's concept of learning to identify what is acquired through communication with intimate others that enables criminal activity. He describes how through this learning process individual gains not only the skills and techniques required to commit the crime, but also the "motives, drive, rationalizations, and attitudes" that accompany the behaviour (Sutherland & Cressey, 1978). The fifth proposition further elaborates upon the issue of criminal motivation: as individuals are surrounded by a "cultural conflict" of competing ideas from both law-abiding citizens and criminals, pro-criminal or anti-criminal intentions are developed based

on learned conceptions of the law as either “favorable” or “unfavorable” (Sutherland & Cressey, 1978: 123). In other words, one develops opinions of the law that either encourage or discourage action. In the sixth proposition, Sutherland argues that an individual becomes a drug addict only when “definitions favorable to violation of law” exceed “definitions unfavorable to violation of law” (Sutherland & Cressey, 1978). In the seventh proposition, Sutherland avoids oversimplifying the social learning processes by describing how “excess definitions” (associations, attitude, and patterns) are affected by four factors: frequency, duration, priority, and intensity” (Sutherland & Cressey, 1978). The eight propositions reiterate the logic behind the criminal learning process. Sutherland explains that, like any other skill or knowledge, the process by which one attains and develops pro-criminal and anti-criminal patterns is the same as any other learning process (Sutherland & Cressey, 1978). Therefore, differential association theory best captures and explains the causes of drug abuse and its influence on the academic performance of secondary school students, and the society at large. The theory demonstrated that drug abuse generally is learned in interaction with others, mostly in intimate groups. According to the theory acts like stealing, smoking, staying away from school, missing tests, and assault are learned in the process of interaction with other drug addicts in society. The theory demonstrated that the act of drug abuse is learned in interaction with others mostly in intimate groups.

Social exchange theory (George Homans, 1958)

Social exchange theory proposed that social behavior is the result of an exchange process. The purpose of this exchange is to maximize benefits and minimize costs. According to this theory, developed by sociologist George Homans, people weigh the potential benefits and risks of social relationships. When the risks outweigh the rewards, people will terminate or abandon that relationship.

Most relationships are made up of a certain amount of give-and-take, but this does not mean that they are always equal. The social exchange suggests that it is the valuing of the benefits and costs of each relationship that determine whether or not we choose to continue a social association. Hence, this theory explains that when people of the same kind of peer relates together they exchange values, morals, norms, and beliefs which are usually replicated when they are alone as individuals in their respective homes, for instance, if an individual who is a gambler mingles with another individual who is a non-gambler, such individual might likely learn gambling techniques from the gambler and replicate such behaviour while alone with other people that are non-gamblers.

Empirical Review

Bediako, Quansah, Omotosho and Hagan (2021) studied on the assessment of peer pressure and sexual adventurism among adolescents in Ghana: The moderating role of child-rearing practices. The study shows that peer pressure is a major reason behind high levels of sexual adventurism.

Ijie and Babalola (2020), using the techniques of the Auto-Regressive Distributed Lag (ADRL) Model, investigated government expenditure on substance abused persons and economic growth in Nigeria, 1993-2017. The bound test result indicates that there is a long-run positive effect of government expenditure on substance abuse on the real growth rate.

Walters (2020) recently explored the possibility that amorality mediates the peer influence effect. In constructing the research design for this study, pro social peer associations were included as moderators of both paths of the mediated peer influence effect: specifically, the path running from delinquent peer associations to empathy and the path running from empathy to subsequent offending were moderated by prosocial peer associations. In contrast to the present study, empathy, another moral system variable, served as the mediating variable rather than proactive criminal thinking. Walters (2020a) adopted a moderated mediation methodology by incorporating moderation and mediation into the same design. According to the results of the investigation, pro social peers predicted higher levels of empathy in individuals with fewer delinquent friends and lower levels of offending in youth with less empathy. This indicates the presence of a biphasic pattern in which pro social peer associations strengthened the peer influence effect by promoting empathy in youth with few delinquent friends and weakened the peer influence effect by] discouraging offending in youth lacking empathy. The current study sought to

replicate these findings using a different sample and a different mediator (i.e., proactive criminal thinking in the form of neutralization beliefs instead of empathy).

Adeyemi & Adejoke (2019) studied Peer group influence on the academic performance of undergraduate students at Babcock University, Ogun State. Results show that there is a significant influence of peer pressure on the academic performance of students.

Henggeler (2019) reviewed the relationship between family transactions and child psychosocial functioning in 65 studies conducted over 30 years and found delinquent behavior to stem from three areas. First, low levels of parental control strategies may be a source of delinquent behavior. Second, if parental controls are present, but are inept or ineffective, youths in these families are at risk for the development of delinquency. And finally, the antisocial behavior of parents, including the degree to which deviant methods of meeting goals are acceptable, seems to be a strong predictor of delinquent behavior in young family members.

Ashrafa, Madya, Ahmadb, and Talib (2019) in their study on the role of parenting and peer pressure in the development of Juvenile delinquent behaviour among higher secondary school children indicated that peer pressure and parenting styles jointly predict delinquency among secondary school children.

Onoyase and Ebebuwa (2018) examined the relationship among Adolescents' developmental characteristics, peer group influence, and their anti-social behaviour. The findings revealed that physical, intellectual, social/emotional characteristics and peer groups influence adolescents' anti-social behaviour. It was recommended that adolescents should be made to indulge in productive leisure time activities where they can dissipate their energies. Furthermore, Esiri (2016), in his study on how peer pressure influences criminal behaviour, found that dimensions of peer pressure influence criminal behaviour in adolescents.

Hanasif (2017) aimed at assessing peer influence and parenting style and whether they influence crime among youths in slums reported that lazier-fair parenting styles and the age factor could predict the involvement of youth in petty crimes within the slums area. Furthermore, the result indicated that authoritarian single parents either rarely involve themselves in petty crimes or never. However, it's noted that the overall authoritarian parenting style nurtures the respondents well thereby becoming good citizens. As further revealed, 18.9% of the respondents from an authoritative parenting style and who are single involve themselves in petty crimes. However, 14.3% of respondents from the same parenting style and who are married get involved in petty crimes. It is indicated that the level of petty crime is much higher for single parents.

Ms. Debajani Nayak (2016) conducted a non-experimental descriptive study to assess the knowledge and practice of substance abuse among adolescents. Socio-demographic variables show that the majority of the participants were Hindus (71%), and 81% were males. In knowledge regarding the prevention and treatment of substance abuse shows that 5.39% agree with the prevention and treatment of substance abuse. As regards physical and psychological aspects of substance abuse shown that 7% feel happy after consuming alcohol, 9% have physical comfort, 9% have good sleep and relax well, and 10% avoid negative motions. The practice of substance abuse results that 56% of students take alcohol and other drugs. 5% of the students started taking drugs and alcohol by watching their parents. In the final statistical analysis, it was found that the association of knowledge score with sociodemographic variables like age, stream of adolescence, and occupation of their parents were significantly associated with 13.1, 4.03, and 6.35 respectively at a level p-value 0.001.

Esiri (2016) examined the Influence of Peer Pressure on the Criminal Behaviour of youths in Nigeria. The study particularly investigated peer pressure in adolescents and how it may influence or create the leverage to nonconformity to societal norms and laws. The study used the framework of social learning and the social control theories and uncovered that the major features of the peer pressure process are identified as group dynamics, delinquent peer subculture, peer approval of delinquent behaviour, and sanctions for non-conformity which include ridicule, mockery, ostracism and even mayhem or assault in some cases. Also, the study highlights acceptance and rejection as key concepts that determine the sway

or glaciation of adolescents to deviant and criminal behaviour. Finally, it concludes that peer pressure exists for conformity and in delinquent subcultures.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

The study employed predictive research design. Predictive research design reveals the predictive relationship that exists between two or more variables (Raj, 2010). The participants that were used for this study are youths in Aguata local government area in Anambra state. Two-hundred (200) youths were selected through the accidental sampling method. The sample comprised of 100 males and 100 females within the age range of 16-35 and mean of 35.6 and standard deviation of 16.78. Three instruments were utilized in this study, the instruments are; Crime Behaviour Rating Scale (CBRS) by Animasahun (2011), Drug Abuse Screening Test by Skinner (1982), and Resistance to Peer Influence Scale (RPI; Steinberg & Monahan, 2007).

4.0 RESULT

Table 1: Descriptive statistics showing mean and standard deviations for all variables

	Mean	Std. Deviation	QAAZN
Criminal behaviour	31.1260	1.24950	200
Drug Abuse	29.8893	1.38182	200
Resistance to Peer Influence	39.7519	2.88925	200

Descriptive data in Table 1 revealed that Criminal behaviour is slightly elevated at $M = 31.1$, $SD = 1.25$ among participants, an indication that it may have been influenced by the presence of drug abuse and resistance peer influence among youths in Aguata local government area of Anambra State.

Table 2: Zero-order correlation matrix showing the relationship among variables of the study: Criminal behaviour, Drug Abuse, and Resistance to Peer Influence among Youths in Aguata Local Government of Anambra State.

Variables	M	SD	1	2	3	4
1 Criminal behaviour	31.12	5.45	1.00			
2 Drug Abuse	29.88	5.18	.805*	-.496*		
3 Resistance Peer Influence	39.75	12.3	.589*	.683	1.00	

* correlation significant at $p < .05$ (2-tailed) ($N = 200$)

Findings from the zero-order correlation in Table 2 showed that the independent variables (drug abuse and resistance to peer influence significantly correlated with the dependent variable (criminal behaviour) at $r = .805$, $p < .05$ ($N = 200$) and $r = .589$, $p < .05$ ($N = 200$) respectively. Also, there was a negative correlation between the independent variables at $r = -.496$, $p < .05$ ($N = 200$). This implies that both drug abuse and resistance to peer influence can predispose youths in Aguata to exhibit criminal behaviour.

Table 3: Moderation regression for the interaction of drug abuse, peer influence, and criminal behaviour among youths in Aguata Local Government of Anambra State

Variables	R ²	Δ R ²	DF	F	B (UC)	β (SC)	T	SE	LLCI	ULCI
Model 1	.37	.02	3(197)	35.23**						
DA					.01	.02*	2.27	.03	.20	.39
PI					-.02	.02*	2.16	.02	-.02	.03
DA* PI					.10	.03**	2.28	0.2	.00	.01

Note: ** = $p < .01$, * = $p < .05$; ** means that the test is significant at .01 level of significance;

Δ R = increase on adjusted R² and F-ratio as a result of the interaction; B (UC) = Unstandardized coefficient; β (SC) = Standardized Coefficients Beta; DA = Drug Abuse, RPI = Resistance to Peer Influence.

Hypothesis one: It states that drug abuse will not significantly predict criminal behaviour among youths in Aguata Local Government in Anambra State. From Table 3, the hypothesis was rejected ($\beta = .02$, $t=2.27$, $p <.05$), indicating that drug abuse significantly predicted criminal behaviour among youths in Aguata Local Government in Anambra State. This implied that drug abuse increases the culture of criminal behaviour among youths in Aguata, Anambra State Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two: it states that resistance to peer influence will not significantly predict criminal behaviour among youths in Aguata Local Government in Anambra State. From Table 3, the hypothesis was rejected ($\beta = .02$, $t= 2.16$, $p<.05$), meaning that resistance to peer influence significantly predicted criminal behaviour among youths in Aguata Local Government in Anambra State. This implied that resistance to peer influence can negatively propel youths in Aguata to exhibit criminal behaviour.

Hypothesis Three: it states that drug abuse and resistance to peer influence will not jointly predict criminal behaviour among youths Aguata Local Government in Anambra State. From Table 3, the hypothesis was rejected. The result of the moderated regression showed that model 1 contributed to 37% variation in the understanding of criminal behaviour among youths, $F (3,197) = 35.23$ at $p <.01$, indicating that drug abuse and resistance to peer influence jointly predicted criminal behaviour among youths in among youths Aguata Local Government in Anambra State. This implied that both drug abuse and resistance to peer influence can predispose youths in Aguata Local Government in Anambra State to exhibit criminal behaviour.

Summary of findings

1. Drug abuse significantly predicted criminal behaviour at ($\beta = .02$, $t=2.27$, $p <.05$)
2. Resistance to peer influence significantly predicted criminal behaviour at ($\beta = .02$, $t= 2.16$, $p<.05$)
3. Drug abuse and resistance to peer influence jointly predicted criminal behaviour at $F (3,197) = 35.23$ at $p <.01$.

5.0 DISCUSSION

The first hypothesis which stated that drug abuse will not significantly predict criminal behaviour among youths in Aguata, Anambra State was rejected. The result showed that Drug abuse positively and significantly predicted criminal behaviour at ($\beta = .02$, $t=2.27$, $p <.05$). This implied that drug abuse increases the culture of criminal behaviour among youths in Aguata, Anambra State Nigeria. These findings corroborate the findings of Usman and Usman, (2012), who showed that drug abuse and violence were correlated and this has made politicians use the youth in causing violence for political interest.

The second hypothesis which stated that resistance to peer influence will not significantly predict criminal behaviour among youths in Aguata, Anambra State was also, rejected. The result showed that resistance to peer influence negatively and significantly predicted crime at ($\beta = .02$, $t= 2.16$, $p<.05$). Which implied that resistance to peer influence can negatively propel youths in Aguata to exhibit criminal behaviour. This finding supported the findings of Farrell and White (2018) who showed a strong positive relationship between resistance to peer pressure and the frequency of drug use as well as criminal behaviour, in which the relationship was found to be stronger among girls than boys.

The third hypothesis which stated that drug abuse and resistance to peer influence will not jointly predict criminal behaviour among youths in Aguata, Anambra State was rejected. The result of the moderated regression showed that model 1 contributed to 37% variation in the understanding of criminal behaviour among youths, $F (3,197) = 35.23$ at $p <.01$, indicating that drug abuse and resistance to peer influence jointly predicted criminal behaviour among youths in Aguata Local Government in Anambra State. This implied that both drug abuse and resistance to peer influence can predispose youths in Aguata Local Government in Anambra State to exhibit criminal behaviour. This finding supported the findings of Warren (2004) explored the developmental conditions under which peers influence adolescents' behaviors, and the moderating effects of autonomy, drug use, attachment, and self-worth.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the study therefore concluded that drug abuse and resistance to peer influence predicted criminal behaviour among youths in Aguata, Anmabra State.

Based on the findings, it is recommended that:

1. There is a crucial need to address drug-related problems among youths. Therefore, the National Campaign against Drug Abuse (NACADA) should review the curriculum to inculcate more values among the youth.
2. Parents are also advised to come up with their responsibilities by giving their children proper training from home as this will, in turn, help their children to manage pressure from their peers.
3. Also, the government should intensify its campaign against drug abuse and criminal behaviour among youths. This is because when people hear more about how dreadful a thing is they tend to avoid it.

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